

Fundamentals of Mathematics for Data Science

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Introduction

Mathematics is the cornerstone of all contemporary sciences. Almost all modern data science techniques, including machine learning, have a deep mathematical infrastructure.

It is obvious that a "Data Scientist" needs different types of science, such as programming ability, the power of judgment about business issues, and a unique analytical and exploratory mindset about data to grow in this field.

One of the biggest challenges in the learning of artificial intelligence is mathematics in artificial intelligence, which many interested people abandon learning because of this issue.

It doesn't matter what kind of relationship you had with math in school. The core concepts used in mathematics are actually very useful for strategic decision-making when designing machine learning models.

So, if you decide to take this career path in data science, you must fall in love with mathematical concepts and implement them in the future as this is one of the most important prerequisites for machine learning and artificial intelligence.

Behind many of the standard data models and structures in data science, there is mathematics that makes them work. It is important to understand the mathematical equations and relations to be a successful data scientist.

Actually, in each step of data science, you will touch a wide range of mathematical concepts and approaches and see how they arise in data science.

Discrete Mathematics

Much of the progress made in mathematics since the 17th century was in the account of differentials and integrals, which were properties of a real number and a function of this set.

The study of these numerous collections led to the emergence of the concepts of coherence and derivation, and for this reason, this mathematics is called continuous mathematics.

But in contrast to this kind of mathematics, there are other concepts in mathematics that can be defined on finite sets and yours. The set of these mathematical concepts is called discrete mathematics.

Discrete mathematics has grown in recent years due to the advancement of computer science.

The most important topics in discrete mathematics are combinatorics, graph theory, mathematical logic, set theory, and preliminary number theory.

Combinatorics

Combinatorics is an area of mathematics primarily concerned with counting, both as a means and an end in obtaining results, and certain properties of finite structures.

It is closely related to many other areas of mathematics and has many applications ranging from logic to statistical physics, from evolutionary biology to computer science, etc.

I recommend starting with an introduction to combinatorics, which basics of this topic are critical for anyone working in Data Science.

Graph theory

In mathematics and computer science, graph theory is the study of graphs. A graph is a set of vertices connected by edges. In simpler terms, a set of points connected by lines is called a graph. The concept of the graph was proposed by Euler in 1736 with a solution to the Königsberg bridge problem and was gradually developed. Graphs are widely used in data science today.

Graphs can be found everywhere around us. One of the most well-known types of graphs in data science are the graphs of social networks.

Mathematical logic and reasoning

The role of reasoning in human life is undeniable. We all need to be empowered in our daily lives or in our professional lives.

The submission of the intellect to the divine gift of reasoning has made it possible for human beings to interact with human beings and to develop various sciences and to grow and develop in various fields.

Argumentation and proof also have a special place in mathematics.

It is not possible to understand mathematics without considering the argument, and it will limit mathematics education to memorizing algorithms.

Familiarity with the methods of reasoning and proof in mathematics will help both to understand mathematics and to develop it.

Set theory

Set theory is the cornerstone of modern mathematics.

The precise definitions of all mathematical concepts are based on set theory.

Furthermore, mathematical inference methods are regulated using a combination of logical reasoning and set theory.

The language of set theory is a common language that logical mathematicians around the world speak and understand.

As if one were to make progress in mathematics or its practical applications, one must become familiar with the basic concepts and results of the set theory and the language in which they are expressed.

Number theory

Number theory is one of the few branches of mathematics whose historical background dates back to ancient times.

At a time when mankind may have had no knowledge of other sciences and had to use numbers to make a living, this branch of mathematics is known as the beginner of its problems.

That is to say, although it is extremely difficult to solve many problems of number theory, their faces can be so simple that they even arouse the interest and curiosity of those who have not seen or hated mathematics education and try to find it.

Calculus

The word “colchicum” is originally from Latin and means a small limestone pebble that is used in an abacus to calculate.

The name of this discipline is a relic of an era when ancient Rome displayed concepts in arithmetic and geometry by placing limestone pebbles on the ground.

In the medieval period, Alhazen (was born in Basra, the region that was part of greater Iran at the time part of the Buyid emirate) derived a formula for the sum of fourth powers.

He used the results to carry out what would now be called an integration of this function, where the formulae for the sums of integral squares and fourth powers allowed him to calculate the volume of a paraboloid.

Modern calculus was developed in 17th-century Europe by Isaac Newton and Gottfried Wilhelm Leibniz (independently of each other, first publishing around the same time) but elements of it appeared in ancient Greece, then in China and the Persia (old name of Iran), and still later again in medieval Europe and in India.

The most important topics in Calculus are the function, limit and continuity, derivative and its applications, integral, certain integrals, methods of integration, hyperbolic functions, vector functions, sequences, and series.

Function

In mathematics, a function is a generator that produces a unique output for each given input.

The reverse is not used to define a function.

This means that a function can even generate the same output for several distinct inputs. In the mathematical expression, the function is a relation in which the first element is paired as input, and the second element is output.

Limit and continuity

In mathematics, the concept of limit is used to express the behavior of a function and to examine this behavior at points on the screen or at infinity.

Limits are used in differential and integral calculus as well as in mathematical analysis to define derivatives as well as the concept of continuity.

Mathematicians have discussed this even before they can express the exact meaning of limit. The ancient Greeks had an understanding of the concept of limit.

For example, Archimedes obtains an approximate value by using the order of perpendicular polygons surrounded by a circle of a single radius, when the number of sides increases indefinitely.

In the Middle Ages, until the Renaissance, various concepts of limit were used to obtain the area of various shapes.

Derivative and its applications

The concept of derivative was not developed until the early 17th century before the French mathematician Pierre de Fermat began to determine the extremes of certain functions.

Fermat found that tangent lines, where the maximum or minimum curve is curved, should be considered that the problem of determining the extreme points of the function depends on solving another problem, namely finding horizontal tangents, trying to solve this general problem.

It was further that led Fermat to discover some of the basic ideas of the derivative concept.

But the concept of derivative in its present form first emerged independently in 1666 by Newton and a few years later by Gottfried Leibniz.

There are various applications of derivatives not only in maths and real life but also in other fields like science, engineering, physics, etc.

Some of the most important topics are rates of change, critical points, finding local and global (extreme) maximum (minimum) values, the shape of a graph, the mean value, optimization problems, and linear approximation.

Integral and methods

In differential and integral calculus, the integral of a function is used to generalize the calculation of the area, volume, mass of a function. Integral of a continuous positive function in the range (a, b) is actually finding the area between the lines $x = a$, $x = b$, and the negative bend F .

So the integral F between a and b is actually the area under the graph. For the first time, Leibniz introduced the governor's symbol for integration.

Certain integrals may be estimated using numerical integral methods. One of the most common methods is called a rectangular method.

It is almost integral. Other popular methods for estimating the integral value are the Simpson method and the trapezoidal method. Although numerical methods do not give us the exact amount of integrals, they sometimes help us a lot when integrals are not functionally solvable or difficult to solve.

The most important definitions in integrals are the Riemann integral and the Lebesgue integral.

Riemann's integral was presented by Bernhard Riemann in 1854, which provided a precise definition of integral.

Hyperbolic functions

In mathematics, hyperbolic functions are analogs of the ordinary trigonometric functions defined for the hyperbola rather than on the circle: just as the points $(\cos t, \sin t)$ form a circle with a unit radius, the points $(\cosh t, \sinh t)$ form the right half of the equilateral hyperbola.

Hyperbolic functions occur in the solutions of many linear differential equations (for example, the equation defining a catenary), of some cubic equations, in calculations of angles and distances in hyperbolic geometry, and of Laplace's equation in Cartesian coordinates.

Laplace's equations are important in many areas of physics, including electromagnetic theory, heat transfer, fluid dynamics, and special relativity.

Vector functions

The word vector means carrier and is derived from a Latin word in the same sense.

A vector is defined as an element of vector space and has n -components in the n -dimensional space. So it is obvious that a vector on a page has two components.

Or it takes three components in three-dimensional space. Vectors have many applications in various sciences such as physics, and without them, many physical components such as speed, acceleration, etc. cannot be interpreted and defined.

The vectors can be added together, subtracted, or multiplied. Each vector has two components, which are the length of the vector and the direction of the vector. Also, each vector has a beginning and an end.

A vector that has a unit length is called a unit vector, and a vector whose length is zero is called a zero or null vector. In mathematics, a unit vector in a normed vector space is a vector of length 1.

A unit vector is often denoted by a lowercase letter with a circumflex, or “hat”. The term direction vector is used to describe a unit vector being used to represent spatial direction, and such quantities are commonly denoted as $\hat{d}$.

Sequences and series

A sequence is a function of the range of natural numbers (or a subset of natural numbers). These functions are widely used in differential and integral calculus and other branches of mathematics. Sometimes, the name of the sequence changes.

For example, in analytic number theory, sequences are called arithmetic functions. There are different types of sequences: real sequence, finite sequence, infinite sequence, boundary sequence, monotone sequence, arithmetic sequence, geometric sequence, convergence sequence, divergent sequence, Fibonacci sequence, Cauchy sequence, triangular number sequence.

A series is a sum of a sequence of terms. That is, a series is a list of numbers with addition operations between them.

Also, there is a variety of series including finite series, infinite series, geometric series, power series, convergence series, diverging series, alternate series, telescopic series, and series with positive sentences.

Trigonometry

Trigonometry is one of the most important branches of mathematics which has various applications in theoretical and practical fields. Among other things, trigonometric functions are used in number theory, music theory, series, Fourier transform, and statistics.

Actually, trigonometry is the branch of mathematics concerned with specific functions of angles and their application to calculations. There are six functions of an angle commonly used in trigonometry.

Their names and abbreviations are sine (sin), cosine (cos), tangent (tan), cotangent (cot), secant (sec), and cosecant (csc). The sine of an acute angle in a right triangle is defined as follows: for a specified angle, the ratio of the length of the opposite side to the angle to the length of the longest side of the triangle (chord) is called the sine of that angle.

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